

**THE PRINCIPLES OF NATIONALITY AND GENERAL HUMANITY
IN THE NATIONAL IDEA IN EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF
PATRIOTISM**

**Tashkent State Pedagogical University, Faculty of History, Department
of “Education of Spirituality and Law”**

Ph.D. Deputy Professor Rahbarov Ulugbek Rahbarovich

Annotation : in this article, the principles of nationalism and universality in the national idea in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism , the issue of the harmony of nationality and universality in the education of the young generation, the formation of moral culture in young people, the feeling of concern for the interests of the Motherland, the harmony of nationality and universality, and the primacy of universal human values based on their interdependence the means of influence are illuminated.

Key words: youth, education, virtue, culture, national idea, morality, culture, value, nation, social - maturity, moral virtue, high - spirituality, national pride, spirituality

The main goal of comprehensive reforms in the field of education and science in the Republic of Uzbekistan educating the young generation morally, spiritually, patriotically and ideologically mature is considered as an urgent task. Including the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev¹ On January 13, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev, in a speech at an extended meeting of the Security Council, focused on the topic "History and duty to future generations" and said, "I would like to emphasize one point on today's auspicious day: the military potential and high moral potential of the Armed Forces of Uzbekistan." It is necessary to turn their power into two great supports. Our glorious history, the bravery of our great ancestors, our indomitable commanders, their wise teaching, "Know the one with a strong wrist, and kill the one with a strong mind and heart" teach us this very truth of life. In this sense, the most important task of all of us is to further improve the system of military education and education of young people in the spirit of military patriotism, national identity, and devotion to our noble values.

¹People's word. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev¹ On January 13, his speech at the holiday event to the defenders of the homeland on the occasion of the 31st anniversary of the establishment of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan. 2020 January 14. Issue #-9.

Therefore, the national idea becomes important because it can embody the interests of all the peoples living in the country and serves to strengthen the development of the society.

The issue of harmony of nationality and universality in the system of the national idea has important scientific, theoretical and practical aspects. First of all, this requires a correct understanding of the concept of "national". The existence of a system that ensures the continuous operation of the national idea shows that the factors that contribute to its regular, continuous operation in different periods are in operation.

Instilling in the hearts of people of different nationalities and peoples the feeling of concern for the interests of the country and the Motherland is an important factor that creates a system. One such factor is the combination of nationalism and universalism in the system of national ideas.

In the system of the national idea, the primacy of universal values is based on the harmony of nationalism and universality, their interdependence. As one of its main principles is related to the idea of humanity, nationality and universality are inextricably linked with each other both as a system and structurally and functionally. In order to further improve the expression of this relationship in the process of systematic work in society, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev issued the Decree No. F-5465 on April 8, 2019 "On measures to develop the concept of developing the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development" ².

3

In the national idea system, in the relationship between nationality and universality, nationalism should not deny universality, and universality should not deny nationality, or one of the two sides should not be allowed to be absolute.

, one of the sociologists of our republic. "The national idea begins to form in the process of self-realization of each person. The formation of a person as a person begins with his self-awareness. ... The sphere of influence of the national idea is extremely wide, and it has its influence on such things as maintaining the identity of the nation, uniting representatives of the nation in the interests of the nation, organizing and defining the directions of development ⁴. From the above, it can be seen that the principles of the national idea are compatible with universal human

²Decree "On measures to develop the concept of development of the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development" <https://lex.uz/docs/3765918>

³Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 8, 2019 No. F-5465 "On measures to develop the concept of development of the national idea at a new stage of Uzbekistan's development".

⁴ Otamuratov S. Philosophy of national development. - Tashkent: Academy, 2005. - B.20, 24-25.

values. The system of the national idea has its own principles, on the basis of which the actual tasks of national development are being implemented.

In our opinion, national consciousness, national thinking is oriented towards the formation of national identity; aimed at uniting the nation; represent the interest of the nation; to be the basis for the formation and strengthening of national pride, pride and responsibility; to be the basis for the formation of a single Motherland mentality among the population of our multi-ethnic country; to be a spiritual and spiritual source of preserving, mastering and passing on national heritage, historical memory to the next generation; aimed at forming the spiritual and spiritual potential of patriotism, nationalism, patriotism and universal humanity in our youth; reflecting the status of our nation as an independent entity; to organize the representatives of nationalities and peoples living side by side with our nation, to live peacefully with them, to treat them with respect, to show them support, to strengthen cooperation and to be a source of the formation of the feelings of a single nation of Uzbekistan based on them; giving spiritual strength and inspiration to make a worthy contribution to the modern civilizations of our nation; To be the theoretical basis for the formation and strengthening of the spirit of national security and national development in the people of Uzbekistan; Reflecting the ideal of a perfect human being constitutes the main national and national principles of the national idea.

The national ideal is obedience to the law in all spheres, respect for human rights and non-discrimination; to live and work in friendship and brotherhood with representatives of different nationalities; respecting the language, religion, and customs of each nation; deep assimilation of worldly knowledge, enlightenment; study the advanced achievements and culture of other nations in various fields; to be free from nationalism, aggressive nationalism and chauvinism; embody the ideas of justice, equality, peace, creativity and democracy; to embody the ideas of religious tolerance; to light the fire of war, to be free from oppressing other countries; it is necessary to demonstrate and enjoy universal democratic principles such as fighting against destructive and malicious ideas and being a factor in the development of constructive ideas .⁵

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⁵The idea of national independence. Textbook. Tashkent: Academy, 2005. - B.222, 223.

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